

CONTEMPLATE ON PSYCHOLOGICAL BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF Gen Z CONSUMERS TOWARDS YOU TUBE ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract:

The study is about the psychological buying behaviour of consumers towards YouTube advertisements. Advertisements play an important role to create awareness among people about the product or service. Earlier advertisements were shown and displayed on television, radio, and newspaper but today's digital media have replaced and conquered the old form of advertisements. In digital media YouTube has become a common platform for advertisements. While watching YouTube, we often come across pre-roll advertisements which sometimes have an option to skip, and mid-roll advertisements which are usually between the content we are watching on YouTube. For conducting a study among the select age group i.e Gen Z customers, a sample size of 120 customers were chosen out of the infinite population of YouTube viewers. The Questionnaire was administered to 120 respondents who are watching YouTube videos regularly within the age group of 18-30 years. For the analysis of data, SPSS software was used. There were two statistical tests conducted for the study are correlation to find the relationship between the variables and Mann Whitney U test was conducted to find any significant difference between the select group of people.

Key Words: Advertisements, YouTube, Pop Up, Buying Behaviour, Pre Roll, Mid Roll & Skip Ad

1. Introduction:

These days we cannot live a single day without internet and undoubtedly it is the most reliable machine "Man" has ever made. Through internet a product is advertised worldwide and advertisement can be in the form of a video. Nowadays, YouTube has become a common platform for advertisement. It is a video sharing website headquartered in San Bruno, California, United States. It was founded on 14th February 2005 by Steve Chen, Jawed Karim and Chad Hurley who were former PayPal employees. YouTube allows users to upload, view and share videos which has a wide variety of content like music clips, educational videos, TV clips, video clips. Any video uploaded on YouTube can also be an advertisement. These video advertisements can be a pre-roll ads, that is the video ad that is played before the content the user has selected. They sometimes have an option to skip the ad after 5 seconds and go to the content selected. They also have mid-roll ads, these ads appear during the content the viewer has selected, and it is usually for 15-20 seconds in length. According to Online Advertisers, mid-roll is better than pre-roll and post-roll advertisements as you are forced to watch it as it is in middle of the video or content you are watching, second you can take an action regarding the ad if you're interested. Post-roll ads are the ads that are placed after the video at the end. It may have least viewership as once the video is over the viewer would either see the next video or close the video. YouTube advertisement cost is totally in control depending upon your budget. Companies only have to pay when someone is engaged with their advertisements. If the advertisement is skipped before 30 seconds or before the advertisement ends they don't have to pay anything. This study is done to know the behaviour and effect of YouTube advertisements on people. It helps us to know how people react to YouTube advertisements, do they skip the advertisement after 5 seconds or they watch the entire advertisement, when there is no skip option available do they watch the advertisement forcefully or they switch to some other work for that particular minute. YouTube: User Device Determines Viewing Behaviour. Christopher Rick, March 24, 2014. This article discusses on how viewer behaviour is affected by the device that is used to watch content on YouTube. According to the article viewers usually spend more time watching YouTube videos on game consoles, mobile phones as compared to desktops. Article states that the average viewing time per video is higher on smart phones and tablets than on desktops. People select content according to the device they are using. Say, if someone has to read an e-book he would refer to read it on tablet or desktop as the screen size is comparatively larger than mobile phones but if they need to read the book while they are travelling they will read on mobile phones so it totally depends on the viewing behaviour.

2. Objectives:

The main aim of my study is to experimentally investigate the effects and behaviour of YouTube advertisements among the select age group of the respondents. Following are the research objectives:

- ✓ To Analyze the behaviour of people toward YouTube advertisements
- ✓ To find out the effect of YouTube advertisements.
- ✓ To Know the effect of YouTube advertisements on their purchasing decision

3. Review of Literature:

You Tube: Christophor Rick, March24, 2014. This article User Device Determines Viewing Behavior discusses on how viewer behavior is affected by the device that is used to watch content on YouTube. According to the article viewers usually spend more time on watching YouTube videos on game consoles, mobile phones as compared to desktops.

Supriya Verma, IJMEI Volume 2 issue 02 Feb 2016 542, Article states management and economics invention that the average viewing time per video is higher on smart phones and tablets than on desktops. People select content according to the device they are using. An article about Affect the Credibility of Your Website. A video on your website that is from some other video player rather than from YouTube will that be more credible than if you embed video from YouTube. It also talks about the advantages and disadvantages of using YouTube. If a brand puts their videos on YouTube the second most popular search engine and if a viewer searches the same content on YouTube then there is a chance by this you can drive traffic to your website. According Online video marketing is swiftly growing, and is getting access to current knowledge of how customers view their marketing moves, which can make a significant impact on perception of their brand. Nowadays, everyone has different opinions; similarly here also every respondent had different opinion about different aspects of embedding video on a website.

Dr. Vasudev A. Modi, 28 December 2014, This research deals with the impact of online advertising on consumer buying behavior in Ahmadabad. In this study, the author talks about various benefits of internet marketing like online branding, reach, cost and consumer preferences. It explains in detail the different types of ad formats used which are pre-roll video advertisement, banner advertisements, social media advertisements, and further explaining the types of online advertisements that is floating ads, pop-up ads, video ads and mobile ads. No doubt internet advertising is effective in creating awareness, buying decisions are changing and half of the respondents are getting influenced by online advertisements. The appearance of advertisements plays an important role in attracting the attention of the viewers.

4. Research Methodology:

4.1 Research Design: The research study is “descriptive” in nature and quantitative research methods have been applied in this study.

4.2 Sample Selection: The sample section method used for the study is “random sample study” .Certain questioners are selected for the sample to verify the entry made on the SPSS tool .the correct entry of the questioners would provide the correct result for the study.

4.3 Geographical Coverage: The questioners are collected in Coimbatore region students. SNR Sons College students and working professionals of the same region. All the questioners’ are filled by YouTube viewers

4.4 Sample Size: Sample size of the study is 120 in which 10 questionnaires are collected as pilot study for the study and 110 are collected as questioner from students and working Professionals.

4.5 Period of Study: The period of the study about YouTube advertisement is 3 months from January 2017 to March 2017

4.6 Statistical Tool Application: Correlation was applied to find the relationship between factors affecting the you tube viewers. Factor analysis was carried out to find the leading factors of the study.

5. Conceptual Study:

YouTube videos: People of age group between 18-34 are the most influenced group. The global Smartphone shipment units reached 1.2 billion in 2014, which is a take away fact that 98% of Smartphone users between the age of 18-34 watch YouTube videos on their Smart phones. The young YouTube audience accounts for the fact that the most viewed or popular video channels are about gaming, music, make-up, fashion and life-style.

6. Analysis and Interpretations:

From the study, the following analysis is done.

Table 1: Gender

S.No	Gender	Frequency	Percent
1	Male	65	59.6
2	Female	44	39.4
	Total	109	100.0

From the above Table 1, 65 person belongs to male gender and 44 person belongs to female gender.

Table 2: Frequency in watching You Tube

S.No	Time Period	Frequency	Percent
1	Daily	47	43.1
2	Weekly	49	45.0
3	Monthly	13	11.9
	Total	109	100.0

From the above Table 2, It shows clearly that 43 percent of people watch YouTube daily and 45 percent of people watch YouTube weekly hence table reveals that most of the people watch YouTube weekly.

Table 3: Hours spend on watching You Tube

S.No	Time	Frequency	Percent
1	5 mins	14	12.8
2	30 mins	45	41.3
3	60 mins	33	30.3
4	more than 60 mins	17	15.6
5	Total	109	100.0

From the Table 3, It shows that 41 percent of people spend watching YouTube 30 minutes in a week and 30 percent of people spend watching YouTube 60 minutes in a week.

Table 4: Kinds of advertisement on You Tube

S.No	Kinds of advertisement on YouTube	Frequency	Percent
1	Pre-Roll	49	45.0
2	Mid-Roll	59	54.8
	Total	109	100.0

(Source: Primary data)

The table 6 shows that 54 percent of YouTube viewers has seen mid roll advertisement. And 45 percent of YouTube viewers have seen pre roll advertisement.

Table 5: Skip the advertisement or watch the advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Watch the Advertisement	41	37.6
2	Skip	54	49.5
3	Sometimes Watch	14	12.8
4	Total	109	100.0

(Source: Primary data)

The table no 5 shows that 49 percent of YouTube viewers have said that they will skip the advertisement while watching the YouTube advertisement and 37 percent have said that they will watch the advertisement while watching the video in YouTube

Table 6: Reasons for skipping the advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Irritating	23	21.1
2	Irrelevant	21	19.3
3	Boring	24	22.0
4	Time Waste	19	17.4
5	Others	6	5.5
6	Data Waste	16	14.7
	Total	109	100.0

(Source: Primary data)

From the above table no 6, 22 percent of YouTube viewers said that it's boring to watch the advertisements played on YouTube, next to it, 21 percent of YouTube viewers said that its irritating to watch the advertisements played on YouTube

Table 7: Tend to watch again after skipping the advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	9	8.3
2	No	61	56.0
3	Sometimes	39	35.8
	Total	109	100.0

(Source: Primary data)

Table no 7 shows that 56 person of YouTube viewers will not tend to watch again after they skip the advertisement and only 9 percent of YouTube viewers will tend to watch the advertisement even after they skip

Table 8: Kind of Advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Advertisement With Good Visuals	20	18.3
2	Trending Advertisement	24	22.0
3	Innovative Advertisement	16	14.7
4	Interesting Advertisement	39	35.8
5	Others	10	9.2

	Total	109	100.0
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Table no 8 reveals that 35.8 percent said that if the advertisement is interesting they would watch it without skipping. 22 percent said that if the advertisement is trending they would watch it without skipping. 18 percent said that if the advertisement contains good visuals they would watch it without skipping. 14.7 percent said that if the advertisement is innovative they would watch it without skipping.

Table 9: Product knowledge provided by advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	12	11.0
2	Agree	63	57.8
3	Neutral	23	21.1
4	Disagree	8	7.3
5	Strongly Disagree	3	2.8
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 9 reveals that 57.8 percent people agree that advertisement is beneficial to them because it provide them useful information about goods and service. 7.3 percent people disagree that advertisement is beneficial to them because it provide them useful information about goods and service.

Table 10: YouTube videos help in enhancing product knowledge

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	18	16.5
2	Agree	65	59.6
3	Neutral	16	14.7
4	Disagree	7	6.4
5	Strongly Disagree	3	2.8
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 10 reveals 59.6 percent people agree that YouTube videos help in enhancing product knowledge. 14.7 percent people said that YouTube videos may or may not help in enhancing product knowledge.

Table 11: YouTube advertisement tempt to buy the product

S.No	Responses	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	48	44.1
2	No	61	55.9
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 11 reveals 55.9 percent YouTube viewers said YouTube advertisements would tempt in buying the product. 44 percent YouTube viewers said YouTube advertisements wont tempt in buying the product.

Table 12: Ended up in buying product by watching YouTube advertisement

S.No	Responses	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	26	23.9
2	No	42	38.5
3	Sometimes	41	37.6
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 12 reveals 38 percent YouTube viewers said they haven't ended up in buying the product by watching YouTube advertisement. 23 percent YouTube viewers said they have ended up in buying the product by watching YouTube advertisement.

Table 13: Influence of YouTube advertisement in buying the product

S.No	Responses	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	37	33.9
2	No	72	66.1
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 13 reveals 66 percent of YouTube viewers said they haven't brought a product only by influence of YouTube advertisement. 39 percent YouTube viewers said they have brought some product only by influence of YouTube advertisement

Table 14: Comparison of two products

S.No	Responses	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	20	18.3
2	No	89	81.7
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 14 reveals 81 percent of YouTube viewers haven't seen the comparison video of two products before buying the product. And only 18 percent of YouTube viewers have seen the comparison video of two products before buying the product

Table 15: Average price of product purchase

S.No	Average Pricing	Frequency	Percent
1	Rs 1 - Rs 100	44	40.4
2	Rs 101 - Rs 500	26	23.9
3	Rs 501 - Rs 1000	19	17.4
4	above Rs 1000	20	18
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 15 reveals 40 percent of YouTube viewers has brought products pricing range from Rs 1 to Rs 100 by influence of YouTube advertisement. And 23 percent of YouTube viewers has brought products pricing range from Rs 101 to Rs 500 by influence of YouTube advertisement.

Table 16: Attractive pop up advertisements on You Tube

S.No	Pop Up advertisements	Frequency	Percent
1	Apparels	9	8.3
2	Footwear	35	32.1
3	Cosmetics	22	20.2
4	education and technology	11	10.1
5	online shopping site " offers"	32	29.4
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 16 reveals 32 percent of YouTube viewers said they attract towards “footwear” pop up advertisement while you watch YouTube videos .29 percent of YouTube viewers said they attract towards “online shopping site offers” pop up advertisement while you watch YouTube videos . and only 8 percent of YouTube viewers said they attract towards “apparels” pop up advertisement while you watch YouTube videos .

Table 17: Languages on You Tube advertisement

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Tamil	33	30.3
2	English	68	62.4
3	Hindi	8	7.3
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 17 reveals 62 percent of YouTube advertisement play in English language.30 percent of YouTube advertisement play in Tamil language. 7 percent of YouTube advertisement play in Hindi language.

Table 18: Brand recognition

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	35	32.1
2	No	74	67.9
	Total	109	100.0

Table no 18 reveals 67 percent said they could recognize the brand within 7 seconds of the advertisement.32 percent said they could not recognize the brand within 7 seconds of the advertisement.

Table 19: Influence of youtube AD

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	31	28.4
2	Agree	40	36.7
3	Neutral	18	16.5
4	Disagree	16	14.7
5	Strongly Disagree	4	3.7

Table no 19 reveals 36 percent of YouTube viewers agree that more time they watch an advertisement that would influence to buy a particular product.28 percent of YouTube viewers strongly agree that more time they watch an advertisement that would influence to buy a particular product. Only 3 percent of YouTube viewers strongly disagree that more time they watch an advertisement that would influence to buy a particular product.

Table 20: Kinds of Online advertisement and its influences

S.No		Frequency	Percent
1	Google ads	23	21.1
2	face book ads	43	39.4
3	YouTube ads	10	9.2
4	Mobile ads	33	30.3
5	Total	109	100.0

From the above table no 20, it is clear that face book advertisements are more influential in buying behaviour of the customers. Also, Mobile advertisements influence the customers with 30 %.

Table 21: Influencing advertisement

	Frequency	Percent
Highly Influenced	26	23.9
Moderately Influenced	50	45.9
Not Influenced	35	33.3
Total	109	100.0

Table no 21 from the above table 45 percent of YouTube viewers said they are moderately influencing by seeing the advertisement .And 33 percent of YouTube viewers said they are not influencing by seeing the advertisement.

- ✓ From the above correlation table no, YouTube viewers can recognize brand in given time because the advertisement provide Beneficial and useful information to the viewers which is 7 seconds or 10 seconds. it gets negative correlation of (-0.485*) though the time given is less, the information is beneficial and useful. hence it is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ YouTube viewers said they get highly influenced by YouTube advertisements that would lead then to buy the product or tempt to buy the product it gives positive correlation (0.592**) hence it has very good influence , And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos has tempted YouTube viewers in buying the products information it gets negative (-352**) correlation hence it has very good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ The correlation table says more YouTube viewers Time spend on watching videos on YouTube would tend to buy the viewers it gets positive (181*) correlation hence it has good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.
- ✓ Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos and the different kinds of advertisement viewer's watch without skipping it gets negative correlation (-278**) hence it has very good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos has provided Beneficial and useful information about the product it gets negative correlation(-100) hence it has good influence
- ✓ Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos has provided product knowledge and information about the product it gets negative correlation (-135) hence it has good influence

- ✓ Advertisement's are influence and which happens when the YouTube views come across advertisements while watching YouTube videos it gets negative correlation (-299**) hence it has very good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ Average price of purchase of a product and watching advertisement while watching YouTube has negative correlation (-254**) hence it has good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
- ✓ 10. More time the viewer spends time on YouTube advertisement they could recognize the brand. YouTube has negative correlation (-325**) hence it has good influence. And Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Table 22: Results of the Correlation Values

		Correlations											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.106	-.083	-.028	-.036	-.124	-.122	-.058	-.009	-.041	.108	-.064
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.272	.388	.770	.709	.198	.207	.552	.925	.673	.265	.508
Time spend on YouTube.	Pearson Correlation		1	.182	.152	.064	-.140	.189*	-.070	.153	-.025	-.227*	-.325**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.058	.115	.507	.146	.050	.472	.113	.794	.018	.001
Watching advertise ment while watching video	Pearson Correlation			1	.278*	-.100	-.135	-.352**	.068	-.299**	.254*	.005	-.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.003	.302	.163	.000	.479	.002	.008	.962	.413
Kind of Advertism ent	Pearson Correlation				1	-.114	-.054	.268**	.179	.095	.039	.117	.098
	Sig. (2-tailed)					.239	.575	.005	.062	.324	.686	.224	.309
	N					109	109	109	109	109	109	109	109
Beneficial for useful informatio n	Pearson Correlation					1	-.023	.072	-.177	.206*	.152	-.010	-.485**
	Sig. (2-tailed)						.811	.455	.065	.031	.114	.920	.000
Product knowledg e	Pearson Correlation						1	.282**	-.106	.161	.135	-.146	.150
	Sig. (2-tailed)							.003	.272	.094	.163	.131	.119
	N							109	109	109	109	109	109
Tempt to buy	Pearson Correlation							1	-.106	.592**	.227*	-.444**	.133
	Sig. (2-tailed)								.272	.000	.018	.000	.169
	N								109	109	109	109	109
Ended in buying	Pearson Correlation								1	-.215*	-.011	.225*	-.183
	Sig. (2-tailed)									.025	.911	.019	.057
	N									109	109	109	109
Advertise ment's influence	Pearson Correlation									1	.051	-.349**	-.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)										.599	.000	.605
Average price	Pearson Correlation										1	-.171	.114
	Sig. (2-tailed)											.076	.240
Pop up ads	Pearson Correlation											1	-.128
	Sig. (2-tailed)												.185
recognize brand in given time	Pearson Correlation												1
	Sig. (2-tailed)												

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results of Mann Whitney U Test:

Ranks:

	Gender (3)	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z VALUE	P VALUE
Beneficial	Male	66	60.30	3979.50	-2.429	0.15
	female	43	46.87	2015.50		
	Total	109				
Product Knowledge	Male	66	55.69	3675.50	-.319	.749
	female	43	53.94	2319.50		
	Total	109				
Quote	Male	66	54.97	3628.00	-.014	.989
	female	43	55.05	2367.00		
	Total	109				
Influencing	Male	66	51.93	3427.50	-1.309	.191
	female	43	59.71	2567.50		
	Total	109				
Buying Behaviour	Male	66	55.38	3655.00	-.166	.868
	female	43	54.42	2340.00		
	Total	109				

The Mann – Whitney U- test is mathematically identical to conduct an independent sample t- test (also called 2-sample t – test) with ranked values. This approach is similar to the step from Pearson’s bivariate correlation coefficient to Spearman’s rho. The U- test, however does apply a “polled ranking of all variables. As revealed by the results in the above Mann – Whitney there is a significant difference between the gender and the variables YouTube advertisement. The difference in the experimental group is Z value = -2.429, P = 0.000<0.01 Hence the factor beneficial in advertisement is significant and all other factors are not significant.

Test Statistics (a):

	Beneficial	Product Knowledge	Quote	Influencing	Buying Behaviour
Mann-Whitney U	1069.500	1373.500	1417.000	1216.500	1394.000
Wilcoxon W	2015.500	2319.500	3628.000	3427.500	2340.000
Z	-2.429	-.319	-.014	-1.309	-.166
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	.749	.989	.191	.868

a Grouping Variable: gender(3)

5. Findings:

The results shows 43% of respondents watch YouTube daily and some of them use mobile to watch YouTube.45% of respondents come across pre-roll advertisements. 55% of respondents come across mid-roll. According to the research 59 % respondents strongly agree that YouTube videos help in enhancing knowledge and 22% agree that advertising is beneficial to consumers because it provides important information about goods and services. 16% of respondents are moderately influenced over their buying behaviour. 28% said that YouTube advertisements are most influential on their buying behaviour. It is recommended to advertise online as it has an impact on their buying behaviour. SPSS software was used for analysing the factors of the selected study.

1	Recognize brand in given time	Beneficial and useful information	(-485**)
2	High influence of YouTube advertisements	Tempt to buy the product	(592**)
3	Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos	tempted YouTube viewers in buying the products	(-352)
4	Time spend on watching videos on YouTube	Tend to buy the products	(181*)
5	Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos	Kinds of advertisements on YouTube.	(-278**)
6	Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos	Beneficial and useful information	(-100)
7	Watching advertisement while watching YouTube videos	Product knowledge and information	(-135)
8	Advertisement’s are influence	advertisements while watching YouTube videos	(-299)
9	Average price of purchase of a product	watching advertisement while watching YouTube	(-254)
10	Time spend on YouTube advertisement	Recognize the brand. YouTube	(-325**)

	they could recognize the brand. YouTube has negative correlation(-325**)		
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6. Conclusion:

From the results and data interpretation, it can be concluded that 56% of respondents watch YouTube every day, 32% of respondents watch YouTube weekly. 64% of respondents watch YouTube through Mobile phones and 31% of respondents use Laptop to access YouTube. 88% of respondents have come across advertisements while watching videos on YouTube and only 5% have never come across advertisements. For this research questionnaire was prepared, for people between 18-35 years. Researcher with the help of the questionnaire collected the primary data and found some facts like most of the respondents see pre-roll advertisements on YouTube. Not only this researcher also found that 64% of respondents are moderately influenced by advertisements over their buying behavior and according to 44% of respondents YouTube advertisements are most influential on their buying behavior. It is also seen that 22% respondents agree with the statement that advertising is beneficial to consumers as it provides important information about goods and services. The focus of the study was to determine the effect and buying behaviour of people toward YouTube advertisements. YouTube advertisements could influence determinants such as unnecessary purchasing and also helps in enhancing knowledge. In today's media oriented society, almost everyone is bombarded continuously with advertising messages including over hundreds of advertisements every day, from television, radio, movies, Internet, newspapers, magazines etc

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